

Radio Science

Supporting Information for

**Observation and Analysis of Anomalous Terrestrial Diffraction
as a Mechanism of Electromagnetic Precursors of Earthquakes**

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Additional Supporting Information

Supporting Data Set - 1
Supporting Data Set - 2

1 Introduction

This file contains the additional supporting data of the observed anomalous radio wave signals that could not be included in the main paper. There are various types of anomalies classified with different landforms and sites, which are linked to the analyses in the main paper.

This file also contains, in the last section, more detailed description of the modeling of the electric charges on the ground surface as the terrestrial surface plasmon by the Drude dispersion function used in the FDTD analysis of the radio wave propagation.

2 Method of High Sensitivity Radio Wave Observation

2.1 Geography of the Radio Wave Observation

The radio broadcast stations and the observation sites that are primarily involved in this study are summarized in Table 1, and their locations are shown in Figure 1. We observe radio waves at two main sites and other supplementary sites from many different broadcast stations over the main island of Japan.

Figure 1: (a) The radio broadcast stations (●) and the observation sites (■) involved in this study. (b) Locations of only the primary radio broadcast stations (▲) and observation stations (■) in this study, and meteorological and ionospheric observation facilities of the Japan Meteorological Agency (JMA) and the National Institute of Communication Technologies (NICT)(●) in the middle part of Japan's main island, for which observation data are compared synchronously. Numbers 1 to 6 in circle (○) denote the epicenter of the earthquakes EQ.1 to EQ.6 in Table 3, respectively. Letters A to D in circle (○) denote the approximate area of other earthquakes detected near the radio wave observation stations, i.e. A: Gifu Hida district, B: Ishikawa Noto district / Noto peninsula, C: Kanagawa west area, and D: Wakayama north area / Kii channel. Thick solid lines are the Median Tectonic Line (west to east) and the Shizuoka-Itoigawa Tectonic Line (south to north), both of which are major fault zones in Japan.

Table 1: List of the radio broadcast and observation sites included in this study. The polarization and the number of elements for the Yagi antennas at the observation sites are shown in parentheses. Polarization notations H and V are for horizontal and vertical polarizations, respectively. Height of antenna is the sum of altitude above sea level and the approximate antenna facility height.

Observation sites:						
Site Name	(Pol., Elem.)	Longitude	Latitude	Height (m)		
For Toyama/Yatsuo:						
Toyama City, Toyama Pref.	(H,5) (V,6)	E137° 11'13"	N36° 41'38"	30		
Yatsuo, Toyama City, Toyama Pref.	(H,3)	E137° 07'51"	N36° 37'10"	30		
For Iwata/Sakai:						
Iwata City, Shizuoka Pref.	(H,5)	E137° 49'20"	N34° 39'20"	4		
Sakai City, Osaka Pref.	(V,5)	E135° 28'30"	N34° 34'01"	17		
Broadcast sites:						
Freq.(MHz)	Power	Site Name	Pol.	Longitude	Latitude	Height (m)
For Toyama/Yatsuo						
77.4	100 W	Iida	H	E137° 52'21"	N35° 27'33"	771
80.9	0 W	(no broadcast)	—	—	—	—
81.9	100 W	Suzu	V	E137° 13'17"	N37° 19'00"	112
82.3	1 kW	Niigata	H	E138° 48'30"	N37° 42'24"	600
86.0	3 kW	Aomori	H	E140° 38'44"	N40° 47'10"	158
88.3	100W	Iida	H	E137° 52'21"	N35° 27'33"	771
89.3	100W	Miyako	H	E142° 00'17"	N39° 37'13"	432
For Iwata/Sakai						
78.9	3 kW	Tsu	H	E136° 26'01"	N34° 43'57"	320
79.2	1 kW	Shizuoka	H	E138° 27'56"	N34° 58'27"	300
80.9	0 W	(no broadcast)	—	—	—	—
82.5	10 kW	Nagoya	H	E136° 58'04"	N35° 08'49"	227
84.7	5 kW	Yokohama	H	E139° 13'51"	N35° 26'29"	1240
88.8	1 kW	Shizuoka	H	E138° 27'56"	N34° 58'27"	300
82.7	10 W	Aritagawa	H	E135° 22'39"	N34° 05'04"	590
83.2	30 W	Hashimoto	H	E135° 32'33"	N34° 17'29"	296
83.4	10 W	Shimokitayama	H	E135° 57'46"	N33° 59'06"	798

2.2 Verification and Long-Term Trends of the Observed Radio Waves

To verify the stability of the observation, the long-term trend of the observed radio wave power is shown in Figure 2 for the radio wave from Niigata to Toyama at 82.3 MHz, and in Figure 3 for the radio wave from Tsu to Iwata at 78.9 MHz. These two time series are shown here as examples because they have the potential to show significant signal variations possibly associated with earthquakes. The trend of the other time series can be found in the accompanying Supporting Data Set - 1 and 2.

In these results, there are some discontinuities and missing data due to the damage of the observation systems by strong winds and aging; the restoration of the system allowed a better installation, and the signal levels increased. It can also be seen that the annual trend of the received radio wave power is that it is slightly weaker in the winter than in the summer; the reason for this has not yet been confirmed, although it is suspected that the difference in the temperature and the humidity of the Earth's surface mainly affects the strength of the diffraction of the radio waves.

Figure 2: Observed power of the horizontally polarized radio wave from Niigata to Toyama at 82.3 MHz for most of the observation period and its annual trends from year 2016 to 2022. In 2022 in (g), there is a discontinuity in the data in February due to the repair of the cable and antenna that had gradually deteriorated by adverse weather; after the repair, they improved even more than the initial installation, and the signal level increased by approximately 10 dBm.

(a) 2018

(b) 2019

(c) 2020

(d) 2021

(e) 2022

Figure 3: Observed power of the horizontally polarized radio wave from Tsu to Iwata at 78.9 MHz for most of the observation period and its annual trends from year 2018 to 2022. In 2019 in (b), there is a period of interruption and missing data due to damage and restoration of the measurement system; this was a major restoration, and the signal level increased by approximately 10 dBm.

3 Polarized Electromagnetic Precursors over Mountainous Region around Kamikochi and Oku-Hotakadake Peak in the Central Part of Japan

We consider a radio wave propagating near the peak of Mt. Oku-Hotakadake in the Kamikochi district, located halfway between a broadcast station in Iida and an observation station in Toyama, as shown in Figure 4. Rectangular-shaped anomalous signals of vertical polarization were frequently observed by the authors around this radio wave path from 2019 to 2020, and some time later, a group of large earthquakes occurred in the Kamikochi district.

Figure 4: Map of the central part of Japan near the Oku-Hotakadake peak (black triangle). The broadcast stations (black circle) in Iida City and in Fukumitsu Town and the observation station (black square) in Toyama City are shown. The epicenters of the earthquakes of Table 2 are shown by red-filled circles at the same location with the Oku-Hotakadake peak. Thick solid lines are a part of the Median Tectonic Line (running from low center to right center) and a part of the Shizuoka-Itoigawa Tectonic Line (running from the seaside to right low). The map was generated with the Generic Mapping Tools (GMT) and the dataset of ETOPO1 Global Relief Model from the NOAA National Centers for Environmental Information, USA. Note the detail of the water surface in the map is partly inaccurate in the ETOPO1 dataset.

Table 2: List of large earthquakes in Kamikochi district discussed in this section. Magnitude M is of JMA. The maximum seismic intensity of Japan scale (Max SI) is also shown.

No.	Epicenter (Longi. Lati.)	M	Date	Time (JST)	depth	Max SI
1	Nagano middle part E137° 39'42" N 36° 13'30"	5.5	April 23, 2020	13:44:22.1	3 km	4
2	Nagano middle part E137° 39'00" N 36° 14'06"	5.0	April 23, 2020	13:57:55.1	5 km	3
3	Nagano middle part E137° 38'12" N 36° 15'06"	5.0	April 26, 2020	02:22:49.4	6 km	3
4	Gifu Hida District E137° 37'42" N 36° 17'00"	5.4	May 19, 2020	13:12:58.1	7 km	4
5	Nagano middle part E137° 38'24" N 36° 15'42"	5.3	May 29, 2020	19:05:14.9	4 km	4

3.1 Observed Polarization Dependent Electromagnetic Precursors

We observe radio waves for the broadcast and observation stations shown in Figure 4. The Iida broadcast station (black circle, E137° 52'21", N35° 27'33", altitude 770 m) is located at a relatively high altitude in Iida City and is surrounded by much higher mountains nearly 3000 m altitude. Thus, with the usual non-plasmonic diffraction by higher mountains, the radio wave may reach the peak of Mt. Oku-Hotakadake (black triangle, E137° 38'53", N36° 17'20", alt. 3189.5 m). The polarization of the radio broadcast wave is horizontal. The Toyama observation station (black square, E137° 11'13", N36° 41'38", alt. 30 m) is located in Toyama City and the antennas are set up on top of a building. We installed antennas of horizontal polarization and vertical polarization in the Toyama observation station for each direction of the target broadcast stations in Iida and in Fukumitsu in Figure 4. The antennas are 5-element or 6-element Yagi antennas with their elements set horizontally or vertically. Note that the elevation angle of the antenna direction is all horizontal, not oriented toward the zenith angle as adopted in [1, 2, 3]. We use the super-narrow-band filters to reduce the noise in the observation systems as written in the main paper, and the anomalous radio wave signals are clearly and steadily detected even in the city center.

In the region of Figure 4, a group of earthquakes occurred during the short period in April and May 2020, as shown in Table 2, and the epicenters are indicated by the red-filled circles in Figure 4. The region is known for its steep mountains, where a group of large earthquakes often occurs. Numerous rectangular-shaped polarized radio wave anomalies were observed as shown in Figures 5, 6 and 7; in the normal state, the signal level was below -100 dBm, but suddenly it increased by about 20 dB and lasted for several hours or even longer and returned to the previous signal level; they look like rectangular pulses. The distance between the Iida broadcast station and the Toyama observation station is approximately 140 km, and there are high mountains in between. Under normal circumstances, it will be impossible for the radio wave to propagate from Iida to Toyama, while it may be possible if the wave is mediated by anomalous mountain diffraction.

(a) 6 years from Jan. 1, 2017 to Dec. 31, 2022

(b) 10 days from Dec. 27, 2016

(c) 10 days from May 6, 2019

Figure 5: Anomalous electromagnetic wave propagation from Iida to Toyama at 88.3MHz since 2016 till 2020 obtained by the authors. Upper diagram shows the radio wave power observed by a vertically polarized antenna and the lower diagram shows those observed by a horizontally polarized antenna. Arrows indicate the time of the anomalous signals appearing like a random-period rectangular-shaped pulse observed mostly for vertical polarization. In (a), to see the long-term perspective of the observed time series, the signals are plotted for the whole period; for the detail of the anomalous signals, see (b) and (c) and the following Figures 6 and 7. In these plots, large black stars indicate the time of the major earthquakes in Kamikochi district for $M5$ to $M5.5$ (JMA); some of which occurred in a particular short period are listed in Table. 2. Small black stars show those of smaller earthquakes of $M4.3$ to $M4.8$. A medium white star shows a group of 49 small earthquakes of $M1.9$ to $M3.1$ in the same region during the short period from November 23 to November 30, 2018. Continue to Figure 6.

(a) 10 days from Dec. 2, 2019

(b) 10 days from Dec. 12, 2019

(c) 10 days from Dec. 31, 2020

Figure 6: Continued from Figure 5. Anomalous electromagnetic wave propagation from Iida to Toyama at 88.3MHz since 2020 till 2022 obtained by the authors. Arrows indicate the time of the anomalous rectangular-shaped pulses. Continue to Figure 7.

(a) 10 days from Apr. 19, 2020

(b) 10 days from Jan. 17, 2020

(c) 10 days from Mar. 11, 2022

Figure 7: Continued from Figure 6. Anomalous electromagnetic wave propagation from Iida to Toyama at 88.3 MHz since 2020 till 2022 obtained by the authors. Arrows indicate the time of the anomalous rectangular-shaped pulses. Star notations show the major earthquakes larger than 5 in magnitude (JMA) in the periods. A group of earthquakes occurred in April and May 2020 and after that period, as in (b) and (c), precursors are seldom seen.

4 Observed Precursors of Earthquakes on the Pacific Side in the Eastern Part of Japan

4.1 Earthquakes Focused in This Section

We have been detecting electromagnetic precursors of earthquakes steadily since we started the observation several years ago. Table 3 is the list of recent earthquakes that we focus on in this study and these are numbered in the order of their magnitude.

The largest event in Table 3 is EQ.1, Fukushima offshore $M7.4$ earthquake on March 16, 2022. In the Tonankai region, where the Iwata observation station is located, the local seismic intensity (SI) was 4, and in the northwest region (or Hokuriku region), where the Toyama observation station is located, the local SI was 5-. Precursory signals of this event have been observed since several days before, and a large and clear anomalous signal was observed one day before the main shock.

Another earthquake EQ.2 Miyagi offshore $M6.9$ occurred on March 20, 2021, one year before EQ.1 at the same location and depth, with the same level of magnitude. For this event, in each region of the Iwata observation station and the Toyama observation station, the local seismic intensity was smaller than that of EQ1, and both 4.

Further examples of the radio wave signals before recent smaller earthquakes would provide some clearer insights into the probability of successful detection of the precursors. An earthquake of a smaller magnitude, EQ.3, Ibaraki offshore $M6.0$ occurred on May 22, 2022, two months after EQ1 at a similar location but in a shallower region. A smaller event, EQ.4, also occurred at a similar location but in a deeper region as compared to other earthquakes, at Ibaraki north $M5.4$ earthquake on Apr.19, 2022. An even smaller event of EQ.5, Ibaraki offshore $M5.3$ earthquake occurred shortly afterward on May 29, 2022, at the south of the Fukushima offshore $M7.4$ epicenter. The last example is the event that occurred inland, EQ.6, Ibaraki south $M4.8$ earthquake on May 5, 2022. We have detected precursory signals for many events during our observation period, and some of the most notable events have been described here. These signals become clearer as the magnitudes increase.

In Figures 8 (a) to (f), the distribution of the seismic intensity of Japan scale is shown for each earthquake. These maps have been publicized by the Japan Meteorological Agency (JMA) in their seismic intensity database. For EQ.1 Fukushima offshore $M7.4$ event, the mechanical geodesic shock spreads over 1,000 km as shown in Figure 8 (a). Hence, despite the independent mechanisms between the electric charges and mechanical shocks, the electric charge carriers may spread over distances as far as those of mechanical shocks; in view of the evidence, electromagnetic precursors have been detected at distances as far as those of earthquakes exemplified in this report. For the EQ.2 Miyagi offshore $M6.9$ event, the shock reached the location of the Iwata observation station and the Toyama observation station. Possible precursory signals are clearly observed in those radio wave data. For the other earthquake examples with magnitudes below 6.0, the mechanical shock of the earthquake was less than 1 on the intensity scale at the observation stations. It is of particular interest to estimate the possible reaching distance of the electric charge carriers even if the mechanical shocks are not reachable, which is suggested by comparing the smaller earthquakes of Figures 8 (c) to (f) with the following radio wave signals.

Figure 8: Map of Japan showing the seismic intensity distribution of earthquakes EQ.1 to EQ.6 in Table 3. These maps are from the Japan Meteorological Agency (JMA) Earthquake Database web pages (<https://www.data.jma.go.jp/eqdb/data/shindo/index.html>), in each corresponding web page of the events. The color indices of the seismic intensities are of JMA; these indices and the epicenter notation are shown as they appear on the original web page. The latitude and longitude labels have been added by the author.

Table 3: List of the earthquakes focused in this study. Epicenters and Magnitudes M are of JMA. The observed maximum seismic intensity of the Japan scale (Max SI) is also shown.

EQ.	Epicenter (Longi. Lati.)	M	Date	Time (JST)	depth	Max SI
1	Fukushima offshore E141° 37'22" N 37° 41'48"	7.4	March 16, 2022	23:36:32.6	57 km	6+
2	Miyagi offshore E141° 37'40" N 38° 28'05"	6.9	March 20, 2021	18:09:44.8	59 km	5+
3	Ibaraki offshore E141° 24'13" N 36° 46'27"	6.0	May 22, 2022	12:24:11.3	5 km	5-
4	Ibaraki north inland E140° 20'51" N 36° 52'38"	5.4	April 19, 2022	8:16:00.3	93 km	5-
5	Ibaraki offshore E140° 58'32" N 36° 14'52"	5.3	May 29, 2022	15:55:22.5	44 km	4
6	Ibaraki south inland E139° 50'41" N 36° 08'26"	4.8	May 5, 2022	18:42:02.1	52 km	4

4.2 Observed Electromagnetic Precursors of Earthquakes

4.2.1 Descriptions on the Observation Data Plots

The observed radio wave signals are shown in Figures 10 to 29 together with other environmental data: local temperature and precipitation, ionogram of the ionospheric E-layer in Kokubunji, geomagnetic field in Kakioka, the magnitude of the earthquake, local seismic intensity of the Japan scale detected in the region of the observation stations, and epicentral district names. These data are publicized officially by JMA and NICT, Japan.

The signal level is monitored also at 80.9 MHz, where no broadcast wave is assigned; this helps to distinguish the noises generated from other wideband electromagnetic sources [4]. The broadcast station and the observation station are noted in the figures for each radio wave plot with the frequency and the power of the wave. The notations '(H)' and '(V)' indicate that the antennas are horizontally and vertically polarized, respectively.

The total geomagnetic field measured by JMA in Kakioka is plotted in these figures to consider whether solar activity affects the radio wave propagation and produces precursor-like signals; the sampling period of the geomagnetic field is one minute, which is appropriately fine to compare with the precursor radio wave signals that vary with the typical time constant of several minutes to hours.

4.2.2 Evidence of Receiving Radio Waves from Distant Locations

It is noteworthy to show that the radio wave signal had reached the Toyama observation station from Niigata over 180 km distance, which may raise the suspicion of exceeding the distance of the line-of-sight propagation of electromagnetic waves. In Figure 9, the data for two radio waves from Niigata at 82.3 MHz and at 79.0 MHz are shown (the third and the fourth slots from above), one of which was for the Niigata FM Port station at 79.0 MHz (the fourth slot), which stopped broadcasting at the end of June 30, 2020, while the other signal at 82.3 MHz (the third slot) has continued broadcasting. From the comparison of these observed signals before and after the time of service termination, it is clear that the radio wave signals had reached Toyama by that time, and that one had stopped and the other is still reaching.

Figure 9: The radio wave power (dBm) from Niigata at 82.3 MHz and at 79.0 MHz observed at the Toyama (TYM) observation station. It also includes the environmental and meteorological data, which will be described in detail in the later section. It is clearly shown here that the broadcast of 79.0 MHz (fourth slot from above) ended at the end of June 30, 2020. "foEs" (second slot from below) denotes the sporadic E-layer critical frequency.

4.2.3 Large Earthquakes and Their Precursors

In Figure 10, clear precursors of sudden increase and decrease are observed during a short time of several hours as highlighted with the yellow background before the main shock of EQ.1 Fukushima offshore $M7.4$ earthquake indicated by a star. The signal level at 80.9 MHz remains the same, indicating that the precursors are not from any other wideband noise. In addition, the weather and the ionogram do not show even small changes, and hence it is considered that the precursors were not caused by the influence of the weather or the ionospheric E-layers. The geomagnetic field also shows no changes around March 16, 2022, suggesting that the anomalous signal was not caused by solar activity or turbulence. In Figure 10, smaller signal variations are seen from March 11 to March 14, 2022, in the data from Tsu at 78.9 MHz. This could be partly due to the smaller earthquakes around March 11 to March 15, 2022, but could also have been influenced by the crustal stress that caused the event of Fukushima offshore $M7.4$ on March 16, 2022.

In Figure 11, precursors are also seen at the Toyama and Yatsuo observation stations in western Japan as highlighted with yellow background before EQ.1. The weather conditions and the 80.9 MHz signal do not change near the Toyama observation station on the day of the event. The time variation of the radio wave power is similar to that of Iwata as in Figure 10. Smaller earthquakes occurred in Ishikawa Noto, Gifu Hida (see areas B and A, respectively, in Figure 1) before EQ.1, and smaller precursor signals are also seen slightly before the smaller earthquakes.

For EQ.2 Miyagi offshore $M6.9$, a large variation is seen in Figure 12 in the 78.9 MHz data from the Tsu broadcast station approximately 2 days before the event. Other data of precipitation, temperature, and ionograms show little change simultaneously with the radio wave signals, suggesting almost no possibility of the influences of meteorological or ionospheric conditions; the 80.9 MHz data remain the same, i.e., there is no influence of wideband noise from other sources. In the same figure, relatively large earthquakes occurred in Wakayama north (see area D in Figure 1), on March 15, 2021, at 0:25:59.3 JST with $M4.6$ depth 4 km; for this event, small precursors were observed on March 12, 2021. It is noteworthy that in Figure 12, the signal variation of 78.9 MHz and 79.2 MHz data on March 15, 2021, at about 1:00 to 4:00 JST, is not an anomaly, but an artificial noise when the radio wave is suspended for regular maintenance of the broadcast stations early on Monday morning. A small signal variation is seen again on March 16, 2021, in the same data; a few hours later, Ibaraki south earthquake $M4.9$ occurred (as listed in the top of Figure 12, but not shown in Figure 1; Ibaraki is on the Pacific side of Japan) on March 16, 2021, at 4:56:18.1 JST at depth 54 km, which may have caused the precursor. The total geomagnetic field shows some ripples on March 20, 2021 as shown in Figure 12; however, the electromagnetic precursors do not coincide with the geomagnetic field ripples, suggesting that the precursors were not generated by the influence of solar activity that may affect the radio wave propagation.

In Figure 13, precursors are seen but are rather ambiguous at the Toyama and Yatsuo observation stations as highlighted in yellow before EQ.2. The main reason for the ambiguity of the precursors would be that the magnitude is smaller and the epicenter is further away for EQ.2 from the Toyama and Yatsuo observation stations as compared to EQ.1. In the same figure, there is no obvious evidence that the meteorological, ionospheric, and geomagnetic field conditions generated the precursor signals, which is also the case for the precursors we have detected so far.

The observation station in Toyama (TYM) is located on the western side of the Japan island, more than 300 km away from the epicenters on the Pacific side. The crustal structure in this district is complicated and consists of intricate large faults. Possibility of charges moving through lithospheric structures and faults [5] and the ground resistivity measurement results [6] do not contradict with the precursors traveling over a long distance to reach the other side of the island.

Figure 10: Observed radio wave power (dBm) at Iwata observation station on the Pacific side of Japan around EQ.1 earthquake in March 2022, together with environmental data observed by national institutes. The main shock of EQ.1 is marked by a star. The possible precursors are highlighted with yellow background. Smaller anomalies for the 78.9 MHz radio wave (fifth slot from above) from March 11 to 14, 2022, are considered due to the preceding smaller earthquakes, and could also be affected by the crustal stress of the $M7.4$ earthquake. "foEs" (second slot from below) denotes the sporadic E-layer critical frequency.

Figure 11: Observed radio wave power (dBm) at Toyama (TYM) and Yatsuo observation stations on the west side of Japan around EQ.1 earthquake in March 2022, together with environmental data observed by national institutes. The main shock of EQ.1 is marked by a star. The possible precursors for the $M7.4$ main shock are highlighted in yellow, which are thinkable because they coincided with the Iwata precursors in Figure 10. Some other precursors are also seen before them, i.e. sharp peak and dip around 00:00 on March 15 (third and fourth slots), and variations on March 12 and 13, which are considered due to the smaller earthquakes nearby in Ishikawa and Gifu, possibly also influenced by crustal stress related to EQ.1, $M7.4$ event.

Figure 12: Observed radio wave power (dBm) at Iwata observation station on the Pacific side of Japan around EQ.2 earthquake in March 2021, together with environmental data observed by national institutes. The main shock of EQ.2 is marked by a star. The precursor with yellow background in the fifth slot from above was sufficiently large as often seen in this 78.9 MHz radio wave; the variation for the 79.2 MHz radio wave (fourth slot) was relatively weaker but considered as a precursor because it appeared simultaneously with that of the 78.9 MHz signal.

Figure 13: Observed radio wave power (dBm) at Toyama (TYM) and Yatsuo observation stations on the west side of Japan around EQ.2 earthquake in March 2021, together with environmental data observed by national institutes. The main shock of EQ.2 is marked by a star. The precursors in the yellow background are rather weak and ambiguous in these results. Other anomalies on March 12 and 16, 2021 (third and fourth slots) could be influenced by the small nearby earthquakes and by the large distant earthquakes in Ibaraki and Fukushima; there is still a possibility that the crustal stress for the $M6.9$ main event affected them.

4.2.4 Antisymmetric Behavior of Anomalous Radio Waves Observed at Two Nearby Stations in Toyama and Yatsuo

It is interesting to note in Figures 11 and 13 that the variations of the anomalous radio wave at 82.3 MHz, observed at two nearby stations in Toyama (TYM, red line) and in Yatsuo (blue line), look anti-symmetric regarding their increase and/or decrease in the signals; these observation stations are only 10 km apart. Such an opposite behavior of the received power cannot be explained by simple meteorological radio ducting or any other influence from ionospheric layers. In other words, when the radio wave power is stronger in Toyama, it is weaker in Yatsuo, and vice versa, which means that the radio wave radiated from Niigata at 82.3 MHz is focused slightly more to the north toward Toyama than toward Yatsuo. This strange behavior often occurs between the observed data at the Toyama and Yatsuo stations. Such beam-steered propagation of a radio wave is well explained by the steep focusing effect of the terrestrial surface plasmon, as shown by the numerical analysis results in the main paper, which depends on the geography, plasma frequency, and thus the strength of the seismic activity [7, 8]. It is often observed that the antisymmetric signals and earthquakes coincide with a high probability.

4.2.5 Comparison of the Precursors of Large Earthquakes

It is noteworthy that the precursors in Figures 10 to 13 show similarity and simultaneity, despite the observation stations being more than 200 km apart; these precursors are plotted together and compared in detail in Figures 14 and 15. Note that the time of the two observation systems is synchronized by the internet time server and the time difference is less than one second.

In Figure 14 (a), the precursors appear simultaneously in the morning of March 16, 2022, in the Toyama (TYM) 82.3 MHz and in Iwata 78.9 MHz data. Intense oscillations (highlighted in yellow) are observed with a period of 1 to 2 hours. These are typical precursors observed before large earthquakes. More detail of the signal exhibits some differences between the signal in Toyama (TYM) 82.3 MHz and that in Iwata 78.9 MHz on the day of the earthquake, as shown in Figure 14 (b), i.e., some sudden drops are seen in Toyama (TYM) 82.3 MHz, while they are not seen in Iwata 78.9 MHz. If the radio wave anomalies occur only in the atmosphere near the epicenter, they must appear simultaneously and identically because the radio wave propagates at the speed of light. The time difference of the anomaly could be evidence that the anomaly occurs not only in the atmosphere but is mediated by other mechanisms such as those on the ground surface and/or subsurface geology.

The simultaneity of the precursors between Toyama (TYM) 82.3 MHz and Iwata 78.9 MHz for EQ.1 in Figure 14 (a) is slightly better than that for EQ.2 in Figure 15 as mentioned above. As can be seen in these results, it is often the case that the anomalous signals have different appearances even when the epicenters are only slightly different.

Figure 14: Expansion and comparison of the precursory signals observed in Iwata, Toyama, and Yatsuo around the EQ.1 earthquake in March 2022. The star symbol shows the time of the earthquake. (a) Comparison of data for 3 days around the day of the earthquake. Yellow highlighted periods are the same as in Figures 10 and 11. (b) More detail on the day of the earthquake.

Figure 15: Expansion and comparison of the precursory signals observed in Iwata, Toyama, and Yatsuo around the EQ.2 earthquake in March 2021. The star symbol shows the time of the earthquake. Yellow-highlighted periods are the same as in Figures 12 and 13.

4.2.6 Long-Term Trend of the Radio Wave Observation Data

Detailed radio wave data are shown below for more extended time period before and after the Fukushima offshore $M7.4$ earthquake on March 16, 2022. Figures 16 to 19 show the data of radio wave power observed at the Toyama / Yatsuo stations (see the sixth and seventh slots from above). Figures 20 to 23 show the data observed at the Iwata / Sakai stations (see the tenth and eleventh slots from above). Those figures also show the radio wave signals from other broadcast stations in Figure 1 and Table 1, as well as the seismic, meteorological, ionospheric and geomagnetic data by the JMA and NICT for reference.

Most of the anomalous signals are highlighted by yellow backgrounds (some are not yet highlighted due to limited capabilities to process all the data for the whole observation period since 2015, of which files are attached as observation datasets); there are varieties of anomalies from small to large in amplitude and period, and among them, those before the Fukushima offshore $M7.4$ earthquake are the largest and most prominent, and even synchronized. It should be noted that these anomalous signals and background noises are relatively smaller in winter than in summer, possibly due to the temperature at the ground surface, but the reason for it is not clear yet and is the subject of further research.

Figure 16: Plots of radio wave data observed in Toyama and Yatsuo compared with meteorological, ionospheric, geomagnetic and seismic data for 10 days from February 21, 2022. Yellow highlights are the anomalous signals of possible earthquake precursors.

Figure 17: Plots of radio wave data observed in Toyama and Yatsuo compared with meteorological, ionospheric, geomagnetic and seismic data for 10 days from March 3, 2022. Yellow highlights are the anomalous signals of possible earthquake precursors.

Figure 18: Plots of radio wave data observed in Toyama and Yatsuo compared with meteorological, ionospheric, geomagnetic and seismic data for 10 days from March 13, 2022. Yellow highlights are the anomalous signals of possible earthquake precursors.

Figure 19: Plots of radio wave data observed in Toyama and Yatsuo compared with meteorological, ionospheric, geomagnetic and seismic data for 10 days from March 23, 2022. Yellow highlights are the anomalous signals of possible earthquake precursors.

Figure 20: Plots of radio wave data observed in Iwata and Sakai compared with meteorological, ionospheric, geomagnetic and seismic data for 10 days from February 21, 2022. Yellow highlights are the anomalous signals of possible earthquake precursors.

Figure 21: Plots of radio wave data observed in Iwata and Sakai compared with meteorological, ionospheric, geomagnetic and seismic data for 10 days from March 3, 2022. Yellow highlights are the anomalous signals of possible earthquake precursors.

Figure 22: Plots of radio wave data observed in Iwata and Sakai compared with meteorological, ionospheric, geomagnetic and seismic data for 10 days from March 13, 2022. Yellow highlights are the anomalous signals of possible earthquake precursors.

Figure 23: Plots of radio wave data observed in Iwata and Sakai compared with meteorological, ionospheric, geomagnetic and seismic data for 10 days from March 23, 2022. Yellow highlights are the anomalous signals of possible earthquake precursors.

4.2.7 Smaller Earthquakes and Their Precursors

The observed anomalous radio wave signal for EQ.3 Ibaraki offshore $M6.0$ earthquake on May 22, 2022, is shown in Figure 24. For this event, the local seismic intensity observed in each region, where the Iwata and the Toyama observation stations are located, was 1 and 3, respectively. The rise time of the precursor signal on May 20, 2022, is much shorter than that of the other earthquakes, which may be attributed to the much shallower epicenter at 5 km in depth than the others. In addition, there is a sudden drop in the data of 78.9 MHz radio wave from Tsu on May 20 at approximately 5:00, which is a typical variation of the precursor signals.

For EQ.4 Ibaraki north $M5.4$ on Apr. 19, 2022, the observed radio wave signals are shown in Figure 25. Clear anomalous signals are seen for the same 82.3 MHz radio wave received by both the Toyama (TYM) and Yatsuo observation stations. Although these observation stations are 10 km apart and the receivers are independent, the anomalous signals vary anti-symmetrically, i.e., as the signal level increases in the Toyama data, the signal level decreases synchronously in the Yatsuo data, which is typical for these stations.

For EQ.5 Ibaraki offshore $M5.3$ on May 29, 2022, the observed radio wave signal is shown in Figure 26. In this case, the anomalous signals appear before and after the event, but they are much larger after the event. The crustal stress may have been changed by the event and continued to be larger; approximately 4 days later, a smaller earthquake of Ibaraki south $M4.3$ occurred in the same district as shown in the same figure.

For EQ.6 Ibaraki south $M4.8$ on May 5, 2022, the observed radio wave signals are shown in Figures 27. In this case, a large anomalous signal appeared before the event and almost disappeared after that. It should be noted that before the anomalous signal, an earthquake of Tokyo Tama East of $M4.6$ occurred, which had a similar magnitude but was located 100 km away from Ibaraki; Tokyo Tama is approximately 30 km west of central Tokyo. The relation between these two events is unknown. However, as written above, it is often the case that only a slight difference in the epicenter leads to a different appearance in the anomalous radio wave signals.

For these relatively small earthquakes, the precursor signals often appear after the event; i.e., anomalous signals start almost simultaneously with the main shock and continue after the event. Such a delay of the anomalous signals for smaller earthquakes could often be seen, whereas for larger earthquakes the anomalous signals are often seen before the main shocks.

Figure 24: Observed radio wave power (dBm) at Iwata observation station on the Pacific side of Japan around EQ.3 Ibaraki offshore $M6.0$ on May 22, 2022, together with environmental data observed by national institutes. The main shock of EQ.3 is marked by a star.

Figure 25: Observed radio wave power (dBm) at Toyama (TYM) and Yatsuo observation stations on the west side of Japan around EQ.4 Ibaraki north $M5.4$ on Apr. 19, 2022, together with environmental data observed by national institutes. The main shock of EQ.4 is marked by a star. Note that anomalous signals continued even after the $M5.4$ event (third and fourth slots), which could be due to some related crustal activity or some other earthquakes.

Figure 26: Observed radio wave power (dBm) at Iwata observation station on the Pacific side of Japan around EQ.5 Ibaraki offshore $M_{5.3}$ on May 29, 2022, together with environmental data observed by national institutes. The main shock of EQ.5 is marked by a star. In this case, it is noted that anomalous signals continued for about a day even after the $M_{5.3}$ main shock (fourth and fifth slots), suggesting the possibility of other earthquakes to occur.

Figure 27: Observed radio wave power (dBm) at Iwata observation station on the Pacific side of Japan around EQ.6 Ibaraki south $M4.8$ on May 5, 2022, together with environmental data observed by national institutes. The main shock of EQ.6 is marked by a star.

4.3 Influences of Natural Phenomena other than Earthquakes on Radio Wave Observations

Here we show the typical signals influenced by other natural phenomena observed in the radio wave signals. Most notable are noise-like signals caused by snow cloud in winter, and enhanced signals caused by the sporadic E-layer of the ionosphere lasting several hours mostly during the day in summer.

A typical observation of the effects of snow cloud is shown in Figure 28, where other environmental data, earthquake records and radio wave signals from other broadcast stations are plotted together. From Jan. 9 to Jan. 12, 2018, typical noise-like signals are seen in the radio wave signals of Iida at 88.3 MHz and of Aomori at 86.0 MHz. Other enhanced signals are seen in those of Niigata at 82.3 MHz, of Suzu at 81.9 MHz, and even at 80.9 MHz where there is no broadcast wave. All these noises are common in this district and are well known to be caused by the discharge and lightning phenomena in snow clouds in winter. The author confirmed the snowfall, lightning, and the typical noises during this period. It is indicated in the plots that the atmospheric temperature was below zero degrees Celsius and the precipitation was recorded simultaneously, which supports these effects.

The effects of the sporadic E-layer are shown in Figure 29. The gray-highlighted parts of the radio wave data from Miyako at 89.3 MHz show the typical signals that the radio wave is reflected by the sporadic E-layer. The reflection of VHF radio waves by sporadic E-layers is well known and has been studied e.g. in [9]. Miyako is the city in the northern part of Japan's main island and the distance in a straight line is approximately 680 km to the Toyama observation station. The radio wave from Miyako is relatively low power of 100 W and is usually unreachable. However, when sporadic E-layer appears, the radio wave is reflected and reaches the distance; this phenomenon typically occurs during the day in summer, but sometimes also occurs at night. In this way, the effect of the sporadic E-layer is easily confirmed by the radio wave from a distance, as shown by the gray highlights in the figure. The occurrence of the sporadic E-layer is also confirmed by the characteristic frequency of the ionogram in Kokubunji and Wakkanai, publicized by NICT, Japan, as shown in the second and third slots from the bottom in Figure 29; the black patterns in the ionogram data synchronize well with the gray highlights in the radio wave data.

These signals are typical and easily distinguishable from the other anomalous radio wave signals and have been removed in considering the precursor signals possibly related to earthquakes. In general, to the best of our experience, the influence of meteorological conditions are not large enough to interfere with the observations of the effects of tectonic and seismic activities.

Figure 28: Plots of environmental, seismic and radio wave data showing the influence of snow cloud on radio wave observation. Noise-like signals are observed from Jan. 9 to Jan. 12, 2018, during which precipitation and low temperature are recorded.

Figure 29: Plots of environmental, seismic and radio wave data showing the influence of the sporadic E-layer of the ionosphere on the radio wave observation. The gray-highlighted parts in the radio wave signals show the typical variation during the day in summer, where radio waves are reflected by the sporadic E-layer and received even from significantly distant low-power broadcast stations.

5 Modeling of the Surface Electric Charges and Anomalous Diffraction and Propagation of Radio Wave

We have modeled the effect of the surface electric charges and anomalous electromagnetic diffraction by the 3D-FDTD method with the frequency-dependent Drude dispersion function [10, 11, 7, 8]. The computation was performed on a Cray CS400 massively parallel supercomputer at Kyoto University, Japan. We used 64 nodes with 2304 central processing unit (CPU) cores with the Message Passing Interface (MPI) libraries and a maximum of 7.8 TB of memory to solve the large-scale problems. The digital elevation model (DEM) of the landform has been publicized by the Geographical Survey Institute (GSI), Japan. The resolution of the original DEM used in this study was approximately 5 m in the horizontal directions. The accuracy of the altitude is 0.3 m in standard deviation, which is the most precise model available from GSI at the time of this study.

The interaction between the terrestrial surface plasmon and radio wave is effectively modeled by the 3D-FDTD method with the Drude dispersion function for the oscillation of electric charge. We define the dielectric properties of the ground, which is loaded with mobile electric charge carriers as in [8]. Damping effects are introduced into the Drude function to account for the lossy objects on the ground, such as trees, plants, and soil.

It has been estimated that the plasma frequency for the electric charge on the ground surface is given by

$$f_p = \frac{1}{2\pi} \sqrt{\frac{n q^2}{\epsilon_0 m^*}}, \quad (1)$$

where the electric charge q of the particle is that of an electron i.e., $q = 1.60 \times 10^{-19}$ C of either positive or negative charge, $\epsilon_0 = 8.85 \times 10^{-12}$ F/m is the permittivity of vacuum. The number density of charged particles n is determined to be at least 10^{15} to 10^{16} m⁻³, which agrees in its order with the theoretical considerations [12], and even larger values are estimated in laboratory experiments [13, 5, 14, 15]. This is not an overestimate for rocks. As n for the ordinary metals is 10^{28} to 10^{29} m⁻³ and those for semiconductors are, e.g., 9.65×10^{15} m⁻³ for intrinsic silicon (Si) and 2.33×10^{19} m⁻³ for intrinsic germanium (Ge) at 300 K, and doped semiconductors have larger carrier density. Even semiconductors host surface plasmons, which are widely investigated for the application of localized resonances of electric charges on nanoparticles [7, 16]. The effective mass of the particle, m^* , contains uncertainty. If positive holes are assumed as the charge carriers in rocks [13], it is conceivable to choose the same order of magnitude as the static mass of an electron m_e , i.e., $m^* \approx m_e$ to $10 m_e$ [8]. It is reported that the lifetimes of the positive holes ranging from a few days to a month have been observed in an experiment using a gabbro tile when stress is kept applied to the tile [15].

In a frequency range lower than f_p , the electric charge carriers oscillate with the outer electric field of the radio wave. Thus, the collective oscillation of the charged particles is induced on the ground surface, i.e., as a surface plasma wave or surface plasmon on the Earth. We consider the boundary between air and ground, i.e., the permittivity of air $\epsilon_1 = \epsilon_0 \epsilon_{r1}$ with $\epsilon_{r1} = 1$ and the complex permittivity of the ground $\epsilon_2 = \epsilon_0 \epsilon_{r2}$ with

$$\epsilon_{r2} = \epsilon'_{r2} - j\epsilon''_{r2} = \epsilon_\infty - j \frac{\sigma}{\epsilon_0 \omega} - \frac{\omega_p^2}{\omega^2 - j\omega\Gamma}, \quad (2)$$

where ϵ'_{r2} and ϵ''_{r2} denote the real and the imaginary parts of the complex permittivity ϵ_{r2} , respectively with j the imaginary unit, ϵ_∞ is the relative permittivity of the ground at the limit of infinite frequency, σ the conductivity of the ground, Γ the damping factor of the Drude dispersion, and ω is the angular frequency of the radio wave. The second term on the right-hand side represents the loss. The third term is the Drude dispersion, which represents the plasma oscillation of the charged particles subjected to an outer electric field [17]. When the permittivity of the ground is larger than that of air, the effective plasma frequency f'_p for the

plasma oscillation on the ground is obtained by letting eq. (2) $\epsilon_{r2} = 0$, and by assuming small losses $\sigma/(\epsilon_0\omega) \ll 1$ and $\Gamma \ll \omega_p$ to give

$$f'_p = \frac{f_p}{\sqrt{\epsilon_\infty}} . \quad (3)$$

From these considerations, it is not unreasonable to assume that the plasma frequency rises at least $f_p = 1000$ MHz in the event of large earthquakes. We also consider relatively large loss factors of Γ in (2) as $\Gamma = 2\pi \times 10^6$ to $2\pi \times 10^8$ rad/s, and assume $\epsilon_\infty = 6$ for the ground and the effective plasma frequency $f'_p = 1000/\sqrt{6} \approx 408$ MHz for all the analysis in this study. The relative permittivity of the ground in Figure 30 shows that, with the Γ used in this study, the necessary conditions for the surface plasmons to be induced, i.e., $\epsilon'_{r2} < 0$ and $|\epsilon'_{r2}| > \epsilon_{r1} = 1$ are still satisfied.

The relation between the frequency and the wavelength, referred to as the dispersion relation, is obtained by solving the complex propagation constant γ rigorously with no approximation [18], consisting of the attenuation constant α and the phase constant $\beta = 2\pi/\lambda$ with λ the wavelength, in terms of the frequency of the wave $f = \omega/(2\pi)$ as a function of the phase constant β with c_0 the velocity of light in vacuum as

$$\gamma = \alpha + j\beta = j\frac{\omega}{c_0} \sqrt{\frac{\epsilon_{r1}\epsilon_{r2}}{\epsilon_{r1} + \epsilon_{r2}}} . \quad (4)$$

The results are shown in the dispersion diagram in Figure 31; the effective plasma frequency, i.e., the flat part of the dispersion curves, is about 400 MHz, which is still sufficiently higher than the radio broadcast frequency of about 70 MHz to 100 MHz. In the diagram, the dispersion curves at the frequency of operation are located in the region to the right of the line of the radio wave in air (dashed line). The diagram thus confirms that a surface plasmon can propagate under these conditions. In all analyses in this study, the incident wave is set to 70 MHz and the propagation conditions for surface plasmons are satisfied. In addition, it is inferred that the charges move from the subsurface to the surface, the path for the mobile charges is in the state of a conductor and therefore can support the surface plasmon. If the crustal activity is stronger and more electric charges are generated, the plasma frequency will be higher and the interaction between the charges and the radio wave will also be stronger, as a result, larger anomalies should be observed in the radio wave signals. For this reason, the strength of the radio wave anomalies is expected to be an appropriate measure of the strength of the crustal and/or seismic activity, even in cases of relatively large losses or damping factors.

Figure 30: Dielectric permittivity model of the ground under electric charge carriers.

Figure 31: Dispersion diagram of the terrestrial surface plasmon with a parameter of the damping factor Γ of Drude dispersion.

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